

Data on species of the genus *Calliostoma* (Vetigastropoda: Trochoidea: Calliostomatidae) on the shelf and bathyal bottoms off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Datos sobre especies del género *Calliostoma* (Vetigastropoda: Trochoidea: Calliostomatidae) en la plataforma y fondos batiales frente a Galicia (NO Península Ibérica)

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ABSTRACT

Three species in the gastropod genus *Calliostoma* are confirmed as living off Galicia, NW Spain: *Calliostoma granulatum* (Born, 1778), *C. maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) and *C. leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896. Empty shells of two more species were found: *C. cleopatra* (Locard, 1898) and *C. conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Even though this is the first record of the rare upper bathyal *C. cleopatra* in Spanish waters, it is unclear whether it currently lives off the Iberian Peninsula.

RESUMEN

Se confirma la presencia de ejemplares vivos de tres especies del género *Calliostoma* en Galicia, NO de España: *Calliostoma granulatum* (Born, 1778), *C. maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) y *C. leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896. Además se han encontrado conchas vacías de otras dos especies: *C. cleopatra* (Locard, 1898) y *C. conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Siendo esta la primera cita en aguas españolas de la rara especie del batial superior *C. cleopatra*, no está claro si actualmente vive en la Península Ibérica.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Calliostomatidae, Spain, NE Atlantic Ocean, Taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Calliostomatidae, España, Atlántico NE taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840 is the most speciose within the family Calliostomatidae comprising over 280 extant species worldwide

(MOLLUSCABASE 2023), ranging from tropical to polar latitudes, from intertidal to bathyal depths (MARSHALL, 1995). *Calliostoma* is an ill-defined genus

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currently encompassing several scantily related species, and will probably be divided once an extensive genetic study is carried out and a deeper knowledge is gained. Most species are specialized carnivores feeding on a large range of food sources, mainly cnidarians (PERRON & TURNER, 1978; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019).

The historic generic grouping of species from the NE Atlantic and the Mediterranean was largely based on shell morphology and is currently lumped under *Calliostoma*. Some are littoral species inhabiting in rocky bottoms, such as *Calliostoma zizyphinum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *C. conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *C. laugierii* (Payraudeau, 1826) species complexes; some species mainly inhabit sedimentary bottoms of the continental shelf, such as the widespread *C. granulatum* (Born, 1778), *C. gubbiolii* Nofroni, 1984 from the Alboran Sea and the neighbouring Atlantic, and *C. lithocolletum* Dautzenberg, 1925, known from Canaries and Seine Seamount; and about 14 bathyal species (“the white *Calliostoma*”), mainly associated to deep-water coral habitats (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019).

The first major works on deep waters *Calliostoma* from the northeastern Atlantic are the ones of DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896, 1897), LOCARD (1898) and DAUTZENBERG (1927). In recent times new works are expanding the knowledge of these deep-water species (VILVENS & SWINNEN, 2003; ROLÁN & SUÁREZ, 2007; LE DUFF, 2015; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011, 2019; DELONGUEVILLE & SCAILLET, 2019; GOFAS & HOFFMAN, 2020; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021).

In order to complete the data provided by the previously mentioned works, in this study, we investigated the calliostomatids collected during several cruises offshore Galicia over the period 2002–2009.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied was obtained in the following expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain) and in the Galicia Bank,

located about 120 nautical miles off the Galicia coast: DIVA-ARTABRIA I (Sep. 2002 and Sep. 2003), VERTIDOS (Sep. 2004), SARRIDAL (Jul. 2007), SELVA (Jul. 2008), and DIVA-ARTABRIA II (Sep.– Oct. 2008 and Sep.– Oct. 2009). We additionally included one additional sample collected during the Fauna Ibérica II cruise (June 1991).

A map of the locations of the sampling stations where the species studied have been obtained is provided in Figure 7.

Sampling methodology and the sorting process of samples were described in PARAPAR & MOREIRA (2009) and in the previous works (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022a, b) with the data related to the cruises carried out. Benthic samples with *Calliostoma* shells were taken in the depth range 146–1293 m by means of naturalist dredge (DRN), Agassiz trawl (AT), rock dredge (DRR) and epibenthic sledge (EBS).

Shells and specimens from the samples studied have been deposited (preserved dry and in 70% ethanol respectively) at the Museo de Historia Natural of the Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Galicia (deposit number MHN-USC 25213), and three specimens from the Fauna Ibérica II in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCS), Madrid.

Abbreviations used:

juv: juvenile
sh: empty shell
spc: shell with soft parts
MHN-USC: Museo de Historia Natural, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain
NMW: Natural History Museum Wien (Vienna), Austria
MNCS: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain
MNHN: Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle (Paris), France

RESULTS

The genus *Calliostoma* is represented in the studied samples by 106 specimens in the bathymetric range of 146–1293 m,

23 of them collected alive (belonging to the species *Calliostoma granulatum* (Born, 1778), *C. maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) and *C. leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896), and 83 as empty shells, including two additional species: *C.*

cleopatra (Locard, 1898) and *C. conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758). A map indicating the locations where the species were found is shown at the end in Figure 7. The data corresponding to each species are detailed below.

SYSTEMATICS

Family CALLIOSTOMATIDAE Thiele, 1924 (1847)

Genus *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840

Type species. *Trochus conulus* Linnaeus, 1758, now accepted as *Calliostoma conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Calliostoma granulatum (Born, 1778) (Fig. 1)

Trochus granulatus Born, 1778: 343

Type material: in NMW, Vienna, not seen.

Material examined: Six shells (five with soft parts) in five samples between 147 and 344 m depth. SPAIN • 1 spc + 1 sh; 43°34.93'N, 08°35.38'W to 43°35.38'N, 08°34.82'W; 151–155 m, 8 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA IAT-150 (2) (Fig. 1) • 1 spc; 43°40.036'N, 08°43.789'W to 43°39.706'N, 08°44.610'W; 198–201 m, 8 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA IAT-200 • 1 spc; 42°29.455'N, 09°17.472'W to 42°31.292'N, 09°19.660'W; 147–149 m, 17 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS 2004-AG - AG-AT-150 • 1 spc; 43°34.11'N, 08°36.53'W to 43°34.69'N, 08°35.59'W; 149–148 m; 14 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA IAT-150 • 1 spc; 44°00'N, 08°32'W to 44°01'N, 08°32'W; 344–343 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-14.

Distribution: *Calliostoma granulatum* is a well-known, common and widespread species in sedimentary bottoms of the European continental shelf from the British Isles to Morocco including

the Macaronesian islands and Mediterranean (FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1977; GRAHAM, 1988; SEGERS *ET AL.*, 2009; TEMPLADO, 2011; LE DUFF & GRALL, 2013; ALF *ET AL.*, 2020).

Calliostoma conulus (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 2)

Trochus conulus Linnaeus, 1758: 598.

Type material: The type material is stored by the Linnean Society of London. Type locality was not stated.

Material examined: One damaged shell at 150–151 m depth (Fig. 2). SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°32.026'N, 08°37.520'W to 43°32.806'N, 08°35.993'W; 150–151 m; 25 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA AT-150.

Distribution: *Calliostoma conulus* lives mainly in littoral rocky bottoms in Brittany (DELONGUEVILLE & SCAILLET, 2001; LE DUFF & GRALL, 2013), Iberian Peninsula and the Canary Islands (TEMPLADO, 2011; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2017: supplementary material), Madeira (SEGERS *ET AL.*, 2009: 71–72), Azores and

in the Mediterranean Sea (ALF *ET AL.*, 2020).

Remarks: It can be distinguished by a conical top spire with almost smooth surface except for a few spiral cords. Only one eroded and broken shell of this littoral species (Fig. 2) was found, likely swept by the currents away from the coast.

Calliostoma cleopatra (Locard, 1898) (Fig. 3)

Zizyphinus cleopatra Locard, 1898: vol. 2, p. 44–45; pl. 2 fig. 20-23

Type material: Two syntypes in MNHN, Paris (MNHN-IM-2000-31095), off Western Sahara.

Material examined: One empty shell at 744–768 m depth (Fig. 3). SPAIN • 1 sh; 42°42.79'N, 11°49.84'W to 42°41.91'N; 11°50.43'W; 768–744 m; 5 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 27-DRR.

Distribution: *Calliostoma cleopatra* is known from the Rockall-Hatton Banks (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011), off Brittany (REYNELL, 1909) to the Western Sahara (LOCARD, 1898) in the depth range 400–1078 m, mainly found in the upper continental slope. In this study, one empty

shell was found on the Galicia Bank at 768–744 m depth (Fig. 3), where it was not reported by GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021).

Remarks: The species can be distinguished by a raised spire, swollen whorls, beaded upper spiral cords and an absence of the umbilicus.

Calliostoma leptophyma Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896 (Fig. 4)

Calliostoma leptophyma Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 482 pl. 21 fig. 6

Zizyphinus laqueatus Locard, 1898: vol. 2, p. 38-40; pl. 2 fig. 16-19

Zizyphinus oppansus Locard, 1898: vol. 2, p. 40-41; pl. 1 fig. 20-23

Type material: not seen, unknown number, probably empty shell. Rocky ground west of Faial, Azores, at 845 m.

Material examined: 57 shells (14 with soft parts) in 23 samples between 407 and 1861 m depth. SPAIN • 3 spc; 42°42.37'N, 11°47.87'W to 42°43.00'N, 11°45.23'W; 769–760; 28. June 1991; Fauna Ibérica II 173A • 3 spc; 43°48.34'N, 08°51.48'W to 43°48.82'N, 08°51.60'W; 579–688 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I, DRN-600 (Fig. 4) • 1 spc; 43°48.42'N, 08°51.45'W to 43°49.16'N, 08°51.09'W; 599–607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 1 sh; 43°48.51'N, 08°51.44'W to 43°49.16'N, 08°51.15'W; 616 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-600 • 1 sh; 43°38.10'N, 09°02.01'W to 43°37.74'N, 09°00.90'W; 836–826 m; 27 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-800 • 4 sh; 43°38.81'N, 09°07.95'W to 43°40.84'N, 09°07.40'W; 999–1001 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; 44°07.49'N, 08°46.99'W to 44°07.67'N, 08°45.22'W; 416–407 m; 18 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-11-2 • 5 sh; 44°11.65'N, 08°58.15'W to 44°11.54'N, 08°57.57'W; 908–1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 4 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.77'N, 08°55.104'W; 581–566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 spc; 44°08.46'N, 09°04.63'W to 44°08.60'N, 09°04.41'W; 917–896 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 6 sh; 43°56.48'N, 08°54.20'W to 43°55.93'N, 08°54.85'W; 620–933 m; 24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 1 sh; 43°34.86'N, 09°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 09°20.71'W; 1010–1112 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04 • 3 spc + 4 sh; 43°33.53'N, 09°13.28'W to 43°33.90'N, 09°12.93'W; 725–737 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-03 • 1 sh; 43°34.19'N, 09°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 09°21.23'W; 1005–1070 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04 • 2 sh; 43°24.64'N, 09°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 09°30.97'W; 880–814 m; 20 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp3-08 • 4 sh; 43°20.00'N, 09°38.06'W to 43°20.63'N, 09°37.59'W; 1268–1293 m; 24 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-15 • 1 sh; 42°51.20'N, 09°44.85'W to 42°52.97'N, 09°44.25'W; 1861–1177 m; 26 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-26 • 1 spc; 43°27.97'N, 09°29.07'W to 43°28.56'N, 09°28.39'W; 859–862 m; 20 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRN-09 • 1 spc; 43°15.71'N, 09°36.93'W to 43°16.37'N, 09°34.81'W; 1056–586 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 18-DRN-p • 1 spc; 43°23.19'N, 09°32.35'W to 43°23.89'N, 09°31.36'W;

(Right page) Figures 1–5. *Calliostoma* from off Galicia. 1. *C. granulatum*, height 28 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA I 2002 AT150. 2. *C. conulus*, height 15 mm, VERTIDOS 2004 GA-AT-150. 3. *C. cleopatra*, height 23 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2009 27-DRR. 4. *C. leptophyma*, height 26 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA I 2003 DRN600. 5. *C. maurolici*, height 14 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2008 25AT.

Figuras 1–5. Calliostoma recolectados frente a Galicia. 1. C. granulatum, altura 28 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA I 2002 AT150. 2. C. conulus, altura 15 mm, VERTIDOS 2004 GA-AT-150. 3. C. cleopatra, altura 23 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2009 27-DRR. 4. C. leptophyma, altura 26 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA I 2003 DRN600. 5. C. maurolici, altura 14 mm, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2008 25AT.

Figure 6. Living specimen of *Calliostoma maurolici*, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2009 27-DRR, 744-768 m. The four characteristic epipodial tentacles of species of the genus are clearly visible.

Figura 6. Ejemplar vivo de Calliostoma maurolici, DIVA-ARTABRIA II 2009 27-DRR, 744-768 m. Son claramente visibles los cuatro tentáculos epipodiales característicos de las especies del género.

866–804 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II, 31-DRN-p • 1 sh; 42°46.44'N, 11°46.70'W to 42°46.34'N, 11°45.06'W; 798–785 m; 4 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 25-AT • 4 sh; 42°42.79'N, 11°49.84'W to 42°40.90'N, 11°51.11'W; 768–744 m; 5 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 27-DRR • 3 sh; 42°46.57'N, 11°51.99'W to 42°47.23'N, 11°51.19'W; 960–965 m; 18 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 92-DRR.

Distribution: *Calliostoma leptophyma* is found from the Hatton, Rockall, and Porcupine Banks, off Brittany, the Azorean Seamounts, the continental slope off Western Sahara in the south, often in association with deep-water corals (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011, 2019; GOFAS & HOFFMAN, 2020; LE DUFF, 2015). LOCARD (1898) reported specimens from off Western Sahara as *Zizyphinus laqueatus*

and *Zizyphinus oppansus*. It is also found off Galicia and on the Galicia Bank in 459–880 m depth range; empty shells in 416–1293 m (ROLÁN & SUÁREZ, 2007; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021; this study).

Remarks: The species can be distinguished by a conical outline and straight profile, spiral ribs variably developed, flattened base of the body whorl, without exposed umbilicus.

Calliostoma maurolici (G. Seguenza, 1876) (Figs. 5, 6)

Trochus (Zizyphinus) maurolici G. Seguenza, 1876: 184

Gibbula obesula Locard, 1898: ex P. Fischer ms.; vol. 2, 47–49, pl. 3 figs 1–4

Calliostoma maurolici: DI GERONIMO & LA PERNA 1997: 418, synonymised *Gibbula obesula* Locard, 1898

Type material. Type locality in a Calabrian (Early Pleistocene) outcrop near Messina, Sicily. The type material is lost. Syntypes of the synonymous *Gibbula obesula* Locard, 1898 from Atlantic Morocco are retained in MNHN (Paris).

Material examined: 41 shells (4 with soft parts) in 14 samples between 480 and 1861 m depth. SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°47.19'N, 08°53.05'W to 43°55.31'N, 08°53.10'W; 770–842 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 1 spc + 2 sh; 43°53.57'N, 08°56.87'W to 43°54.01'N, 08°56.96'W; 965–974 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 5 sh; 43°38.81'N, 09°07.95'W to 43°39.84'N,

Figure 7. Distribution map off Galicia (NW Spain) with stations where the studied shells and specimens of *Calliostoma* have been found. Stations with *C. maurolici* in red, *C. leptophyma* in yellow, *C. granulatum* in green, *C. cleopatra* in purple and *C. conulus* in blue. Bathymetry data source : GEBCO, depth contour intervals 500 m.

Figura 7. Mapa de distribución frente a Galicia (NO de España) con estaciones donde se han encontrado las conchas y ejemplares de *Calliostoma* estudiados. Estaciones con *C. maurolici* en rojo, *C. leptophyma* en amarillo, *C. granulatum* en verde, *C. cleopatra* en morado y *C. conulus* en azul. Fuente de datos batimétricos: GEBCO, isobatas 500 m.

09°07.40'W; 999–1001 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 480–600 m; 19 Apr. 2007; SARRIDAL 2007 SARRI-2 • 5 sh; 44°11.65'N, 08°58.15'W to 44°11.54'N, 08°57.57'W; 908–1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 spc + 10 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.30'W to 44°08.77'N, 08°55.10'W; 581–566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 43°56.51'N, 08°49.87'W to 43°57.45'N, 08°49.75'W; 781–839 m; 21 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-16-1 • 1 sh; 43°42.29'N, 08°49.80'W to 43°43.02'N, 08°49.24'W; 629–542 m; 23 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-17 • 7 sh; 43°56.48'N, 08°54.20'W to 43°55.93'N, 08°54.85'W; 620–933 m; 24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 1 sh; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709–728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-25 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 42°51.20'N, 09°43.85'W to 42°52.97'N, 09°44.25'W; 1861–1177 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-26 • 1 sh; 42°46.44'N, 11°46.70'W to 42°46.34'N, 11°45.06'W, 798–770 m, 4 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 25-AT (Fig. 5) • 1 sh; 42°42.60'N, 11°50.06'W to 42°41.05'N, 11°51.03'W, 791–770 m, 5 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 27-AT • 1 spc; 42°42.79'N, 11°49.84'W to 42°41.9170'N, 11°50.4282'W; 744–768 m; 5 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II 27-DDR (Fig. 6).

Distribution: Fossil in bathyal Pleistocene outcrops (G. Seguenza 1876). LOCARD (1898) reported syntypes of the synonymised *Gibbula obesula* off western

Morocco. The species has a wide NE Atlantic distribution, from the Rockall Bank in the north to the continental slope off Morocco in the south and the

Azorean Seamounts in the west. It is a common inhabitant of deep-water coral communities (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020). *Calliostoma maurolici* also lives on the continental slope off Galicia and on the Galicia Bank (IBARROLA *ET AL.*, 2011; GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021; this study). In this

study shells were found in a bathymetrical range of 480–1293 m; live specimens in 710–974 m, in which the soft parts presented a uniform orange color (Fig. 6).

Remarks: It is distinguished from the other species by its deep umbilicus (Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION

In this study, three *Calliostoma* species were found alive off Galicia: *C. granulatum*, *C. maurolici* and *C. leptophyma*. The former *C. granulatum* lives on the upper shelf, down to about 350 m. The latter *C. maurolici* and *C. leptophyma* are upper bathyal species and they are often associated with living hard corals as well as with other large filter feeders in 300–1000 m. *C. conulus* and *C. cleopatra* were only found as empty shells. *C. conulus* lives subtidally to about 150 m. *C. cleopatra* is an upper bathyal species, occasionally confused with *C. leptophyma*. The species is very rare and mostly found associated with deep-water corals. The two more common and widespread bathyal species *C. leptophyma* and *C. maurolici* are also found on the Galicia Bank. The rare *C. cleopatra* is here reported (as empty shell) and it will be added to the malacofauna of

Spanish waters, updating the national check list of GOFAS *ET AL.* (2017). ROLÁN & PEDROSA (1981) reported a live-collected *C. leptophyma* misidentified as *C. cf. cleopatra* from the Galicia Bank.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALF A., BRENZINGER B., HASZPRUNAR G., SCHRÖDL M. & SCHWABE E. 2020. *A Guide to Marine Molluscs of Europe*. ConchBooks, Harxheim, 803 pp.
- BORN I. VON. 1778. *Index rerum naturalium Musei Cæsarei Vindobonensis*. Pars I.ma. Testacea. Verzeichniß der natürlichen Seltenheiten des k. k. Naturalien Cabinets zu Wien. Erster Theil. Schalthiere. [1-40], 1-458, [1-82]. Vindobonae [Vienna]; (Kraus).
- DAUTZENBERG P. 1927. *Mollusques provenant des campagnes scientifiques du Prince Albert Ier de Monaco dans l'Océan Atlantique et dans le Golfe de Gascogne. Résultats des campagnes scientifiques accomplies sur son yacht par Albert Ier Prince Souverain de Monaco*, LXXII. Imprimerie de Monaco, Monaco, 401 pp., 9 pls.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1896. *Campagnes scientifiques de S.A. le Prince Albert Ier de Monaco. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse-Alice 1888–1895*. 1. Mollusques Gastéropodes. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 9: 395–498, pls 15–22.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1897. *Campagnes scientifiques de S.A. le Prince Albert Ier de Monaco. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse-Alice 1888–1896*. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 10: 139–234, pl. 3–7.
- DELONGUEVILLE C. & SCAILLET R. 2001. Confirmation de la présence de *Calliostoma conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758) dans les eaux du Finistère (Bretagne - France). *Novapex*, 2 (1): 20.

- DELONGUEVILLE C. & SCAILLET R. 2019. First record of *Calliostoma caroli* Dautzenberg, 1927 (Gastropoda: Calliostomatidae) alive in Icelandic waters. *Novapex*, 20 (4): 101–109.
- FRETTER V. & GRAHAM A. 1977. The Prosobranch Molluscs of Britain and Denmark. Part 2. Trochacea. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, Supplement 3: 39–100.
- GERONIMO I. DI & LA PERNA R. 1997. Pleistocene bathyal molluscan assemblages from southern Italy. *Rivista Italiana di Paleontologia e Stratigrafia*, 103 (3): 389–426.
- GOFAS S. & HOFFMAN L. 2020. Deep-water Calliostomatidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain. *Iberus*, 38 (2): 195–211.
- GOFAS S., LUQUE Á.A., OLIVER J.D., TEMPLADO J. & SERRANO A. 2021. The Mollusca of Galicia Bank (NE Atlantic Ocean). *European Journal of Taxonomy*, 785: 1–114.
- GOFAS S., LUQUE Á.A., TEMPLADO J. & SALAS C. 2017. A national checklist of marine Mollusca in Spanish waters. *Scientia Marina*, 81 (2): 241–254.
- GRAHAM A. 1988. Molluscs: Prosobranch and Pyramidellid Gastropods. *Synopsis of the British Fauna (New Series)*, No. 2 (2nd ed.), E.J. Brill / Dr. W. Backhuys, Leiden, the Netherlands: 662 pp.
- HOFFMAN L., BEUCK L., VAN HEUGTEN B., LAVALEYE M.S.S. & FREIWALD A. 2019. Last snails standing since the Early Pleistocene, a tale of Calliostomatidae (Gastropoda) living in deep-water coral habitats in the north-eastern Atlantic. *Zootaxa*. 4613 (1): 93–110.
- HOFFMAN L., VAN HEUGTEN B. & LAVALEYE M.S.S. 2011. Gastropoda (Mollusca) from the Rockall and Hatton Banks, northeastern Atlantic Ocean. Part 2. *Miscellanea Malacologica*, 4 (6): 85–118.
- IBARROLA T.P., ROLÁN E. & LÓPEZ P.R. 2011. Nueva información sobre *Calliostoma obesulum* (Archaeogastropoda, Calliostomatidae) procedente del cañón de Avilés, N de la península Ibérica. *Noticiario SEM*, 56: 44–49.
- LE DUFF M. 2015. Contribution à la connaissance de la distribution géographique et bathymétrique de *Calliostoma leptophyma* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (Gastropoda, Calliostomatidae). *An aod - Les cahiers naturalistes de l'Observatoire marin*, IV (2): 25–28.
- LE DUFF M. & GRALL J. 2013. *Calliostoma conulus* (Linnaeus, 1758): une espèce bretonne bien discrète. *An aod - Les cahiers naturalistes de l'Observatoire marin*, vol II (2): 23–27.
- LINNAEUS C. 1758. *Systema Naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis*. Editio decima, reformata. Laurentius Salvius: Holmiae. Vol 1: 824 pp.
- LOCARD A. 1898. Mollusques testacés. *Expéditions Scientifiques du "Travailleur" et du "Talisman" pendant les années 1880, 1881, 1882, 1883*. Editor Masson & Cie, Paris, Vol 2: 515 pp., pl. 1–18.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1995. A Revision of the Recent *Calliostoma*. Species of New Zealand (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Trochoidea). *The Nautilus*, 108 (4): 83–127.
- MOLLUSCABASE EDs. 2023. MolluscaBase. *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840. Accessed through: World Register of Marine Species at: <https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=138584> on 2023-06-28
- OLIVER J. D., GOFAS S., URGORRI V., DÍAZ-AGRAS G., TEMPLADO J. 2022a. Rissoiidae Gastropods of the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain). *Zootaxa*, 5196 (1): 1–45., available online at <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5196.1.1>
- OLIVER J. D., HORRO J., URGORRI V., ROLÁN E. & TEMPLADO J. 2022b. Conoidean gastropods of the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Iberus*, 40 (2): 363–447
- PARAPAR J. & MOREIRA J. 2009. Polychaeta of the 'DIVA-Artabria I' project (cruise 2002) in the continental shelf and upper slope off Galicia (NW Spain). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 50: 57–78.
- PERRON F.E. & TURNER R.D. 1978. The feeding behaviour and diet of *Calliostoma occidentale*, a coelenterate-associated prosobranch gastropod. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 44: 100–103.
- REYNELL A. 1909. The Mollusca collected by the "Huxley" from the North Side of the Bay of Biscay, in August, 1906. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 8 (4): 359–391.
- ROLÁN E. & PEDROSA G.P.G. 1981. Molluscs collected at the Galicia Bank (Spain). *La Conchiglia*, 150–151: 6–7, 10, 15.
- ROLÁN E. & SUÁREZ M. 2007. Primera cita de *Calliostoma leptophyma* (Mollusca, Calliostomatidae) para aguas de la Península Ibérica. *Noticiario SEM*, 47: 39–43.
- SEGERS W., SWINNEN F. & DE PRINS R. 2009. *Marine molluscs of the Portuguese province of Madeira. Madeira and Selvagens Archipelago*. Snoeck Publishers, Zwijndrecht, Belgium. 612 pp.
- SEGUENZA G. 1876. Studi stratigrafici sulla formazione pliocenica dell'Italia meridionale. *Bollettino del Reale Comitato Geologico d'Italia*, Roma, 7: 179–189.

- SWAINSON W. 1840. *A treatise on malacology or the natural classification of shells and shellfish*. Longman, London viii + 419 pp.
- TEMPLADO J. 2011. Familia Calliostomatidae. Vol 1: 118–120. In Gofas S., Moreno D. & Salas C. (Coords.): *Moluscos marinos de Andalucía*. Servicio de Publicaciones e Intercambio Científico, Universidad de Málaga.
- THIELE J. 1924. Revision des Systems der Trochacea. *Mitteilungen aus dem Zoologischen Museum in Berlin*, 11 (1): 47–74.
- VILVENS C. & SWINNEN F. 2003. Description of *Calliostoma heugteni* n. sp. (Gastropoda: Trochidae: Calliostomatidae). *Novapex*. 4 (4): 119-123.